

**A MEMORANDUM ON THE PROPER HUMAN SEXUAL RIGHTS AND
GHANAIAN FAMILY VALUES BILL 2021**

SUBMITTED TO

**THE COMMITTEE ON LEGAL, CONSTITUTIONAL AND
PARLIAMENTARY AFFAIRS, PARLIAMENT OF GHANA**

BY

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MEMORANDUM

Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021

TO: The Honourable Chairman and Members, Committee on Legal, Constitutional and Parliamentary Affairs, Parliament of Ghana

FROM: [REDACTED] Humanists International, Freedom of Religion and Belief Leadership Network (FoRBLN) and Member (Former President) of Humanist Association of Ghana

SUBJECT: Memorandum - Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021

DATE: September 29, 2021.

CC: Right Honourable Speaker of Parliament and Honourable Members of Parliament, Ghana.

I am grateful to Parliament for the invitation and opportunity for Ghanaian members of the general public to submit this memorandum to assist the Committee in its review and consideration of the Proposed Bill.

I write this Memorandum as a Concerned Ghanaian citizen and a representative of two (2) International Organizations of which I am Board Member. Namely, Humanists International, Freedom of Religion and Belief Leadership Network (FoRBLN) and a Member of a Registered Ghanaian NGO, Humanist Association of Ghana.

Humanists International is the global representative body of the humanist movement, uniting a diversity of non-religious organizations and individuals. We want everyone to live a life of dignity in a world where universal human rights are respected and protected, and where states uphold secularism.¹

FoRBLN is a network of parliamentarians and belief leaders from 8 countries across Africa and South Asia who are dedicated to promoting freedom of religion or belief in their national and local communities. FoRBLN exists to address the legislative barriers to freedom of religion or belief and the social mores that support societal hostility towards groups and individuals on account of their religion or belief.²

The Humanist Association of Ghana (HAG) is a volunteer non-governmental organization (NGO) of Atheists/Agnostics living in Ghana who subscribe to the philosophy of Secular Humanism as a life stance, defend Universal Human rights and promote critical thinking. HAG is a member of Humanists International (HI) and Young Humanists International (YHI).³

I, [REDACTED] would like to state unequivocally that I am not in support of the Bill. I would like to demonstrate why this Bill is against everything I love and respect about my country of birth, its citizens, Our Independent sovereign State, Our Freedom, our Democracy, Our Government and most importantly, Our Constitution.

As Human Beings, there is the need to understand as the famous poet Alfred George Gardiner in his work "Pebbles on the Seashore", summed up most beautifully. "A person's freedom ends where another man's freedom begins." This fact has been affirmed from Justice Oliver Wendell Holmes to John Stuart Mill and Abraham Lincoln.⁴

The following sections of the Bill should please be scrutinized and reconsidered.

Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill first proposed by the National Coalition for Proper Human Sexual Rights and Family Values seeks to suggest that they intend to define what is 'proper' for Humans in terms of their sexuality and also attempt to define and impose their ideas of what they term to be 'Ghanaian'. Ghana, as a country is a diverse and inclusive society of people from various histories, tribes, religious and non-religious belief systems and cultures all of which are protected and enshrined in our Constitution and therefore should not be amended or reinterpreted by any number of people to infringe on Human rights.

In the Bill, The Coalition mentions the recent closure of an LGBT advocacy center and the calls for it to be shut down but failed to mention how so many other Ghanaians also spoke up about their support for the Center and their disappointment of its closure. The Center, which was the

first of its kind was to support the various NGOs and individuals get the much needed help from our education, healthcare and security agencies to curb the constant abuse and discrimination of Real and Perceived LGBT+ persons against Blackmail, Stigmatization, lack of employment, high suicidal rates, domestic abuse, sexual assault, mob lynching and emotional abuses, etc. that are prevalent in the country and have been researched and documented by Human Rights Watch. This Bill was therefore borne out of the homophobia and fear of the Coalition without the proper understanding of the event for the Office Opening, the work of LGBTI groups or without engaging with the participants and stakeholders of the LGBT+ Community. There has been no advocacy to promote sexual activity between same sex in Ghana. In fact, this is almost impossible as being an LGBTI+ person is a natural phenomenon and one cannot choose, teach or force another to change their sexual orientation. The only activities of all Advocates and Activists, NGOs and Human Rights groups has been the protection of the rights of Ghanaian citizens of their rights to life, education, housing, medical care, safety and security as enshrined in the Ghanaian Constitution, the African Union and the United Nations.⁵

The Coalition also failed to mention their affiliation with the World Congress of Families (WCF), an American Far-Right Christian extremist group tagged as a HATE group. The WCF was added to the list of organizations designated by the Southern Poverty Law Center as anti-LGBTI+ hate groups in February 2014 for its involvement with the 2013 Russian LGBT propaganda law and opposing LGBTI+ rights internationally. This group supported the Coalition to organize the first Anti-LGBT conference in Accra in November 2019. The WCF have been notorious for imposing their fundamentalist ideas of patriarchy, misogyny, Islamophobia, white supremacy and Homophobia in the United States of America and other parts of the world.^{6 7 8 9}

The statement in the proposed Bill as follows “LGBT+ activities threaten the concept of family and the associated value systems that are central to the social structure of all ethnic groups in Ghana.” is a fallacious statement in that, it is based on widespread assumption. In fact, although colonialism sought to erase all aspects of our culture especially that of LGBT+ persons in our society, there still remains much research and data to confirm that various tribes that became the Gold Coast and the Republic of Ghana as we know today, lived harmoniously, recognized and acknowledged the existence of LGBT+ persons as we know of today. Our Ancestors lived peacefully with the knowledge that a minority of every population were naturally LGBTI persons. One such example is a Book on aspects of the Nzema culture “Agonwole agyale: the marriage between two persons of the same sex among the Nzema of southwestern Ghana” was published in 1973 documenting this history.¹⁰

There is also no evidence that the recognition and protection of LGBT+ rights as Humans would threaten the concept of family as every country that is LGBT+ friendly has not had a decrease in their population based on this. Homosexuality has never been criminalized in Benin, Burkina Faso, Ivory Coast, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Djibouti, Equatorial Guinea, Madagascar, Mali, Niger, and Rwanda. It has been decriminalized in Angola, Botswana, Cape

Verde, Gabon, Guinea-Bissau, Lesotho, Mozambique, São Tomé and Príncipe, the Seychelles and South Africa. South Africa was the fifth country in the world to legalize same-sex marriage in November of 2006.¹¹

Our Ghanaian culture teaches us that a child is raised by the entire village and therefore, the concept of family in our culture depicts not just that of a heterosexual married couple but also includes various adult members of the family of sound mind regardless of their gender identity and sexual orientation.

In the “Interpretation” section of the Bill, there is misinterpretation of certain definitions. i.e.

Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual - the definitions in the Bill seeks to join an identity with a sexual activity which is not so. Being Lesbian, Gay or Bisexual, is a natural, social identity as heterosexuality and not all people who identify as Lesbian, Gay or Bisexual necessarily have sexual intercourse, therefore it would be false to assume so as stipulated in the proposed Bill.

“Prohibition against undermining proper human sexual rights and Ghanaian family values” seeks to impose one’s opinion of what it means to have Proper Sexual Rights and what it means to be Ghanaian. This section also seeks to infringe on the right to Freedom of Speech and Expression.

“Duty to report” would increase the violence, abuse and discrimination against Perceived or Real LGBTI+ persons and makes anyone and everyone in Ghana a potential target for accusation, arrest and prosecution. It also allows the infringement of the right to privacy.

“Prohibition of LGBTTQQAAP+ and related activities' ' targets Perceived or Real LGBTI+ persons from Heterosexuals who engage in the same acts. This section would also promote the infringement of the right to privacy of consenting adults of sound mind. It also places acts of Bestiality in the same category as LGBTI+ rights which it is not as LGBTI+ rights only refers to the sexual orientation, gender and identity of consenting same-sex adults of sound mind. This is a tactic used by Homophobic propaganda to undermine the understanding of LGBTI+ persons. Accusations of ‘pansexual activity’ would be open to interpretation and discretion of the complainant since this is based on the false premise of an incorrect definition that seeks to join the identity of a pansexual person to an activity which is not always the case and can be used to target anybody who uses a sex toy or alternative in the privacy of their room which is an infringement of the right to privacy and discriminates against LGBTI+ persons when heterosexuals may also use sex toys for sexual gratification. This section also seeks to infringe

on the right to Freedom of Speech and Expression. Also, there has never been any advocacy for same-sex marriage by any group or individuals in Ghana.

“Keeping a brothel for a prohibited sexual activity” seeks to incorrectly infer that all LGBTI+ persons are involved in prostitution and sex work. It also seeks to criminalize housing of Perceived or Real LGBTI+ persons by family members, landlords / landladies or landowners for the acquisition of property thereby insinuating that LGBTI+ persons should be rendered homeless, displaced and disowned by Family. This is an infringement to the right to Housing.

“Prohibition of gross indecency” would be open to interpretation and discretion of the complainant and seeks to infringe on the right to Freedom of Speech and Expression.

“Prohibition of propaganda of, promotion of and advocacy for activities prohibited under this Act” seeks to undermine Advocacy for Human Rights as Propaganda and would not only stifle but halt and set back the activities of Activists and Organizations to curb the prevalence of abuse, violence and discrimination meted out to Perceived or Real LGBTI+ persons and therefore this would increase and would put the lives and livelihoods of the LGBTI+ Community at risk. It would also make Research, Data gathering and analysis difficult as Stakeholders in the Healthcare Industry, Academics and Security Forces would not have adequate information to assist them in their work. Organizations such as CHRAJ, The Ghana Aids Commission, the Ministry of Health, Ministry of Gender, Children and Social Protection, Amnesty International, Human Rights Watch and the Human Rights Council would have their hands tied on issues concerning the health, security and safety of Perceived or Real LGBTI+ persons.^{12 13 14 15}

This section also seeks to introduce censorship and seeks to infringe on the right to Freedom of Speech and Expression.

“Prohibition of propaganda of, promotion of and advocacy for activities directed at a child” places acts of Paedophilia in the same category as LGBTI+ rights which it is not as LGBTI+ rights only refers to the sexual orientation, gender and identity of consenting same-sex adults of sound mind. This is another tactic used by Homophobic propaganda to undermine the understanding of LGBTI+ persons and their Rights. Under this prohibition, this section also seeks to undermine the power of the media and journalism in hearing both sides of the ‘story’ and to introduce censorship and seeks to infringe on the right to Freedom of Speech and Rights to Association.

“Prohibition of funding or sponsorship for prohibited activities” is a prohibition set to undermine the work of Individual Activists and Organizations that need funding to protect the rights of Perceived or Real LGBTI+ persons from abuse, violence and discrimination.

“Disbandment Of LGBTTTQQAAP+ group, society, association, club or organisation” and “Prohibition of LGBTTTQQAAP+ group, society, association, club or organisation” is an infringement on the Right to Association and Assembly.

“Prohibition of adoption order for LGBTTTQQAAP+ persons' ' and “Prohibition of grant of fosterage for LGBTTTQQAAP+persons' ' are sections that seek to undermine the right to parent based on sexual orientation, gender and identity which is discriminatory. This is being used to insinuate that Perceived or Real LGBTI+ persons are not capable of good parenting which is in contradiction of tons of evidence to show that whereas many heterosexual couples have unplanned pregnancies, abandon the children and leave them to their fate, there have been Same - sex couples that are more than capable of adopting these children and providing them with good homes that has no influence on the children’s natural born sexual orientation or gender identity.

“Protection of victims of prohibited sexual activities” is fallacious as LGBTI+ rights only refers to the sexual orientation, gender and identity of consenting same-sex adults of sound mind and therefore, there is no ‘victim’. In fact, Activists in Ghana have been fighting the high rate of sexual harassment, sexual assault and gang rape of Perceived or Real LGBTI+ persons especially towards Lesbians and Bisexual women by Heterosexuals. This section also places acts of Paedophilia in the same category as LGBTI+ rights which it is not as falsely insinuated.

“Flexible sentencing” seeks to introduce forms of emotional and physical torture to threaten Perceived or Real LGBTI+ persons to falsely ‘confess’ and ‘recant’ being LGBTI+ persons for lesser sentences and also to force allegedly accused persons to accept to partake in Gay Conversion Therapy in the name of “‘approved’ medical help or ‘approved’ medical treatment” against their will. This sections seeks to impose Gay Conversion therapy, an idea that being LGBTI+ is viewed as a ‘challenge’, ‘illness’ or ‘disability’ that can be ‘fixed’ which is not true as it is a natural, social part of Human biology as Heterosexuality and not based on the choice of the individual. The American Psychiatric Association defined being gay as having a mental illness until 1973 when this definition was removed and The World Health Organization (WHO) removed Homosexuality from its list of diseases and mental illnesses on the 17th of May 1990. Beyond studies focused solely on reparative therapy, broader research clearly demonstrates the significant harm that societal prejudice and family rejection has on lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender and queer (LGBTQ) people, particularly youth. Furthermore, there is significant

anecdotal evidence of harm to LGBTQ people resulting from attempts to change their sexual orientation and gender identity. Based on this body of evidence, every major medical and mental health organization in the United States has issued a statement condemning the use of conversion therapy.

Psychiatrist Dr. L. Spitzer, who once offered a flawed study on reparative therapy, has since denounced the study and has apologized for endorsing the practice.

Several Lawmakers in the USA have condemned this abhorrent practice including Jerry Brown, Governor of California who said: "These practices have no basis in science or medicine and they will now be relegated to the dustbin of quackery."

The Documentary "Cured" demonstrates the harm that came from the introduction of Gay Conversion Therapy in the USA.^{16 17}

"Prohibition of extrajudicial treatment" is a section of the Bill which also seeks to view being LGBTI+ as a 'challenge', 'illness' or 'disability' that can be 'fixed' which is not true as stated above. It also seeks to legitimize Homophobia and the promotion of misinformation to increase homophobia which would further increase the spate of violence and discrimination against Perceived or Real LGBTI+ persons.

"Assistance for questioning and intersex persons" and the "Regulations" sections would also promote the use of Gay Conversion therapy which is a dangerous psychological torturous practice not approved by any International Scientific study or Organization. This section also seeks to force Intersex persons to perform gender realignment surgery. According to Kevin G. Behrens, Surgery for intersex infants should be delayed until individuals are able to decide for themselves, except where it is a medical necessity.

In July 2017, three former US Surgeons-General, wrote that they believed "there is insufficient evidence that growing up with atypical genitalia leads to psychosocial distress," and "while there is little evidence that cosmetic infant genitoplasty is necessary to reduce psychological damage, evidence does show that the surgery itself can cause severe and irreversible physical harm and emotional distress." They said: "These surgeries violate an individual's right to personal autonomy over their own future." The three doctors concluded.^{18 19}

"Consequential amendments" would also seek to bring censorship and infringement on the right to Freedom of Speech and Expression.

Given this analysis of the Bill, It would be safe to say that the entire Bill would be detrimental to the safety, security and well - being of all Ghanaians, LGBTI+ or otherwise and is an affront to the rights of every Ghanaian citizen. There are many law-abiding citizens that go about their daily lives peacefully in their communities and contribute to the development of the Country including tax-paying citizens such Teachers, doctors, nurses, lawyers, farmers, mechanics, etc. who belong to family units and also help contribute to the welfare of other relatives regardless of their sex and sexual orientation. This divisive Bill would be a deterrent to the growth of Ghana.

LGBTI+ RIGHTS are also Human Rights and it is very much entrenched in our Ghanaian Constitution. The following Articles of our Constitution clearly show this.

- Article 12[2]: “Every person in Ghana, whatever his race, place of origin, political opinion, colour, religion, creed or gender shall be entitled to the fundamental human rights and freedoms of the individual contained in this Chapter but subject to respect for the rights and freedoms of others and for the public interest.”

- Article 17[1] Right to equality before the law.

- Article 17[2] states that “...a person shall not be discriminated against on grounds of gender, race, colour, ethnic origin, religion, creed or social or economic status.”¹⁹

Ghana has also signed a number of treaties on Human rights with various International Bodies such as the United Nations which has passed several resolutions specifically on the rights of LGBT+ persons in the world as seen below:

United Nations Resolutions - Sexual orientation and gender identity

Human Rights Council

Protection against violence and discrimination based on sexual orientation and gender identity (adopted 30 June 2016) - A/HRC/RES/32/2 E F S R C A

Human Rights Council resolution - Human rights, sexual orientation and gender identity (adopted 17 June 2011) - A/HRC/RES/17/19 E F S R C A

Human Rights Council resolution - Human rights, sexual orientation and gender identity (adopted 26 September 2014) - A/HRC/RES/27/32 E F S R C A²⁰

The Bill would also seek to set Ghana Back from achieving its Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) before 2030 such as Ensure healthy lives and promote wellbeing for all at all ages,

Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all, Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls, Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all, Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels.^{21 22 23 24}

The Bill would also seek to set Ghana Back from achieving Freedom of religion or belief which also implies Freedom from Religion and Belief. Ghana must be guided by the principles set out in Article 18 of the United Nations Declaration on Human Rights (UNDHR) on the right to freedom of thought, conscience, religion or belief. Therefore, a group's rights to FoRB should not infringe on the rights of others. Many Christian groups across the world have also come to understand the importance of upholding the Human rights of LGBTI+ persons and acknowledge the damage done to others from homophobia using Religion as a tool. In recent times, Methodist Church allowed same-sex marriage in 'momentous' vote, As far back as 1978, the Presbyterian Church has called for civil rights for all people, regardless of sexual orientation. Pope Francis made news by voicing his support for same-sex civil unions – legal arrangements that give gay and lesbian couples many of the same rights as married opposite-sex couples. The Catholic Church teaches that, as a person does not choose to be either homosexual or heterosexual, being gay is not inherently sinful. The archbishops of Canterbury and York, Justin Welby and Stephen Cottrell respectively, said in a joint foreword to the “Living in Love and Faith” resources that the church had caused, and continued to cause, “hurt and unnecessary suffering”. “For such acts, each of us, and the Church collectively, should be deeply ashamed and repentant,” wrote the leader of the Church of England and its second-most senior figure.

According to a recent survey by Public Religion Research Center, more than half (52%) of American Muslims agreed that "society should approve of homosexuality." A growing number of Islamic scholars, mainly in the West, have started re-examining Islamic teachings on same-sex relationships and whether a blanket condemnation of LGBTQ people is a misinterpretation.^{25 26 27}

28 29 30 31

This Bill would also bring a lot of Diplomatic issues concerning Ghana's relations with other countries who respect the Rights of LGBTI+ Persons and their citizens may want to visit, work and invest in Ghana may choose not to do so. Ghana's Tourism, Industrial, Private Business and Security sector would be affected thereby destabilizing our economy. There is also likely to be a Brain Drain as many Ghanaians for fear of persecution as Perceived or Real LGBTI+ persons may choose to immigrate to other countries for a better life many of whom would be our tax-paying citizens who have done no harm to anyone based on their gender identity and sexual orientation.

Furthermore, the Bill would seek to bring about an overwhelming increase in the already prevalent state of violence and discrimination in Ghana which would leave many victims in fear of reporting as it would be in violation of the Bill itself and due to the non-existence of Allies, Activists and Organizations to assist these victims, it would be most impossible to come to the aid of victims.

In conclusion, I would like to sincerely appeal to the Right Honourable Speaker and Honourable Members of Parliament of the Republic of Ghana to kindly reconsider the passage of this Bill for the safety, security and development of the citizens of Ghana they represent.

THANK YOU

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